

The Francisco “Pancho” Villa Statue: Tucson’s Welcome Mat

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Introduction: Visibility, Interpretation, and Controversy

Motorists exiting the I-10 and approaching downtown Tucson on Broadway Boulevard or Congress Street from the west encounter a tree-lined, triangular grassy median, positioned like a symbolic welcome mat at the city’s threshold and framed by modern concrete buildings. A statue is one of the first sights to greet them. Here, in one of the city’s most visible and once-celebrated public squares, the site of the old, but not forgotten, San Agustín Church, stands a seven-ton, fourteen-foot bronze equestrian sculpture.¹ Astride his wild-eyed, rearing mount, the rider appears either to be in the midst of a violent fight or triumphantly celebrating a victory. Those familiar with the history of United States–Mexico relations and folklore immediately recognize the likeness of Francisco “Pancho” Villa on his horse, *Siete Leguas* (Seven Leagues). For nearly three decades, this statue has found itself caught in a tempest of debates among the citizens of Tucson and throughout the U.S.–Mexico border region, the most recent being the movement to restrict immigration and suppress the freedoms of migrants from south of the border.

In the years leading up to and since 1981, when the statue was installed, opinions and memories of Villa’s character and legacy often appeared in the local media. The city’s two major papers, the *Arizona Daily Star* and the *Tucson Daily Citizen*, actively shaped and influenced the public debate. This essay relies primarily on their coverage and on what they considered newsworthy. In the end, however, reporters and editorials that negatively portrayed Villa’s past and the statue, and even the shunning of the statue’s unveiling by the city’s mayor, could not dissuade large numbers of Mexicans and Mexican Americans from rallying to embrace and celebrate the statue’s arrival in 1981. It is also important to note that borders, defense, and sovereignty have historically been considered masculine concerns. Thus, male voices are overrepresented in this essay because, even by the 1980s, women were seldom acknowledged in public discourse as authorities on territorial defense or the “threat” of an invading revolutionary.

Although Villa stands prominently memorialized in downtown Tucson, there is no information near the statue that attempts to contextualize the revolutionary’s history, his relationship to the United States, or his connection to the city. Instead, visitors find only a simple plaque on the base of the statue stating that Mexico gave Arizona the statue as a gesture of friendship in 1981. Public historians critical of synthesized and standardized explanations on historical markers would likely approve of the absence of interpretation, especially given the controversy surrounding this statue. They propose that commemorative plaques, more often than not, provide uncomplicated narratives that discourage spectators from engaging critically with commemorated sites, and these signposts also represent attempts to control memory.² In contrast, as a public piece of art, the Villa statue pushes spectators to construct their own narratives based on their subjective understandings of history and to confront the most immediate questions: Why this statue? Why this location? In addition to raising issues regarding Mexican–U.S. relations

¹ The nearby historical marker in this square reminds visitors that the former, long demolished San Agustín Church once stood there.

² John R. Gillis, ed., *Commemorations: The Politics of National Identity* (Princeton, N. J.: Princeton University Press, 1994), 17.

and history, it compels viewers to consider not just what is commemorated, but also what is deliberately left unmarked and why. There are many reasons the statue feels out of place to some, but for others, it belongs exactly where it is.

In Tucson, sixty miles from the Mexican border, responses to the statue have ranged from pride to hostility. When veteran Jack Frost from Show Low learned of the statue in the papers, he reportedly said, “It put me in a state of shock. I’ve been pacing the floors since.”³ On the other side of the spectrum, many Mexican Americans, migrants, and immigrant rights activists in Tucson view the statue as a symbol of more open borders in a city with a deep Mexican past and a long history as a gateway for migrants from the south. They see the statue as “a goodwill gesture and as an honor for a hero.”⁴ Thus, the Pancho Villa statue in downtown Tucson resonates differently with various publics, revealing deep divisions and unresolved tensions over borders, history, and public memory that continue to shape the city.

Understanding these divided reactions requires looking at how Tucson’s leaders have reshaped the city’s identity and landscape, often by distancing themselves from its Mexican past. Although Tucson originated as an Indian, Spanish, and, later, Mexican place, twentieth-century boosters consciously attempted to distance themselves from this past in order to solidify Tucson’s image as an “American” city. Civic leaders targeted for destruction the most densely populated area in the city, occupied mostly by Mexican Americans and Sonoran-style structures, as part of their urban renewal agenda in the late 1960s. Tearing down the oldest neighborhood also obliterated much of the physical evidence of the city’s strong Mexican presence and past.⁵ Many in Tucson, however, remember that the site on which this bronze statue now sits as a large section of venerated and communal space of the former church plaza known as “La Placita,” that was demolished by the city three decades ago to “revitalize” downtown.⁶

Villa’s Historical Context and Border Significance

In 1916, the revolutionary made headlines across the world when his troops crossed the U.S.–Mexico border and killed seventeen people in Columbus, New Mexico. Newspapers widely reported that during this rampage, Villa roared, “Death to the gringos!” fanning the flames of fear throughout the border region. In response to the bloodshed, which U.S. leaders denounced as a blatant violation of an international boundary, President Woodrow Wilson ordered General John J. “Black Jack” Pershing and five thousand troops into Mexico to apprehend and punish the “villain.” The so-called Punitive Expedition quickly grew to more than 10,000 troops, outnumbering Villa’s forces by a factor of twenty. The expedition also held a technological advantage, fielding a squadron of eight airplanes. Though Pershing’s troops penetrated 350 miles

³ Joe Watt, “Villa-Plagued Veteran Wants Statue Removed,” *Arizona Daily Star* (hereafter *Star*), June 22, 1983, C1.

⁴ Michael A. Chihak, “Villa in Place in Downtown Park,” *Tucson Daily Citizen* (hereafter *Citizen*), June 30, 1981, F (section front).

⁵ I write about the erasure of Tucson’s Mexican past and present in *La Calle Spatial Conflicts and Urban Renewal in a Southwest City* (Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2010). See also William Deverell, in *Whitewashed Adobe: The Rise of Los Angeles and the Remaking of its Mexican Past* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2004), who argues that exclusions and boundaries served to solidify systems of social control that increased the visibility or “out of placeness” of Mexican people. On consigning Mexican people to the past in promotional campaigns designed to maintain social control, see also Phoebe S. Kropp, *California Vieja: Culture and Memory in a Modern American Place* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2006).

⁶ Abigail A. Van Slyck, “What the Bishop Learned: The Importance of Claiming Space at Tucson’s Church Plaza,” *Journal of Arizona History* (Summer 1998): 121–140. See also my chapter “La Placita Committee: Claiming Place and Challenging Historical Memory,” in *Mapping Memories and Migrations: Locating Boricua and Chicana Histories*, ed. Vicki L. Ruiz and John R. Chávez (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2008), 44–68.

into Mexico, they failed to capture Villa, who credited the allegiance and assistance of the Mexican people for tipping the scales in his favor. Villa's "underdog" status, his unrepentant stance, his ability to elude Pershing's forces, and his masterful horsemanship made him a legend throughout Latin America and the U.S. Southwest and earned him the epithet "Centaur of the North."⁷

Although the Arizona–Sonora border area played an important role in the Mexican Revolution, no definitive history of the Villa–Tucson connection exists. News of Mexico's bloody civil war (1910–20) and Villa's notoriety as an armed revolutionary consistently appeared in mainstream media across the United States. The armed conflict occasionally crossed into Southern Arizona. Some prominent hardware and sporting goods merchants in Tucson profited handsomely from selling legal and illegal arms to various factions of the revolution, but these lopsided commercial exchanges that benefited the U.S. economy were rarely mentioned in the press.⁸ A few accounts assert that in the midst of revolution in early January 1913, Villa spent four days in Tucson to ensure his safety and arrange for the purchase of more arms.⁹

Villa's Columbus attack heightened fear and distrust of Mexican people on the U.S. side of the border. Villa's defiance, combined with suspicions about Tucson's large Mexican American population and its substantial Hiaki or Yoeme population (also known as Yaqui in English), convinced many Tucsonans that their city might be Villa's next target. At the same time, admiration for Villa ran deep in Southern Arizona. The mayor of nearby Nogales, Arizona, even expressed open support for the revolution. For all these reasons, some Tucsonans feared they were surrounded by *villistas* and at risk of imminent attack. Protectionist groups sprang up to defend the city. As evidence of the pervasiveness of these fears, male faculty members at the University of Arizona, formed a volunteer militia to guard the university. "All male professors and staff members were armed... "We used to take time out [from their drills] and get into long arguments," recalled history professor Howard A. Hubbard, "over whether we would march down the Nogales road and meet the Yaquis outside town or stay on campus and fight a defensive battle."¹⁰ Anti-Villa sentiment also accounts for the standing admiration bestowed on Pershing by University of Arizona officials. In 1920, they invited General Pershing to dedicate the new fountain on campus in front of Old Main.¹¹

⁷ The best source for biographical information on Villa is Friedrich Katz, *The Life and Times of Pancho Villa* (Stanford, California: Stanford University Press, 1998), 560–582. The Columbus incident adds credence to the hypersensationalized media coverage of the Mexican Revolution and of Villa in particular. Although reporters claimed he led the raid, Villa stayed on the Mexican side of the border and did not take active role in the attack on Columbus. Up to this point, Villa idolized the U.S. and attempted to remain "friends." Some theories hold that Villa felt betrayed when the U.S. government intervened to aid one of his adversaries by moving troops into Sonora. Some also speculate that Villa attacked Columbus in response to twenty Mexicans being burned alive in El Paso. Villa had also paid an arms dealer in Columbus who failed to deliver weapons and who also refused to return the money. It must also be remembered that Columbus housed a military fort and was not solely a "civilian" settlement. Over one hundred of Villa's troops also lost their lives in this attack.

⁸ Don M. Coerver and Linda B. Hall, *Revolution on the Border: The United States and Mexico, 1910–1920* (Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 1988).

⁹ "Tucsonian Says Dad Saw Villa Here around 1913," *Citizen*, May 15, 1981, 3, and Martín Luis Guzmán, *Memoirs of Pancho Villa* (Austin: University of Texas Press, 1965), 90.

¹⁰ Howard Hubbard, as quoted in Douglas D. Martin, *The Lamp in the Desert: The Story of the University of Arizona* (Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 1960), 118–119.

¹¹ "Gen. Pershing Here," *Citizen*, January 30, 1920, 1.

Villa Comes to Tucson: A Gift from Mexico

Half a century later, Villa's exploits again became fodder for local news stories as the Mexican government began to rehabilitate his legacy in 1967. Despite some minor protests, his name appeared in gold letters on the wall of the Federal Chamber of Deputies in Mexico City.¹² Villa was officially granted an additional honored place in Mexican history in 1976, when President Luis Echeverría Álvarez ordered that his remains be placed in one of the pillars of the Monument to the Revolution in Mexico City, alongside those of other revolutionary heroes. With this monument, which has become "a sacred temple of the nation," according to historian Thomas Benjamin, Mexico sought to "heal the wounds of memory." As President Echeverría proclaimed, "We have consolidated one Mexican revolutionary thesis above the divergences of the past."¹³

The idea and act that led to the statue culminated in 1981, when the Republic of Mexico presented the Villa statue to Arizona as a gift of friendship. The timing coincided with a period when Arizona's economic policy and business leaders sought to strengthen trade and commercial relations with Mexico. An identical statue of Villa stands on a traffic island on Avenida División del Norte in Mexico City, and at least five streets, among countless others throughout the country, are named in his honor.¹⁴

At a cost of about \$260,000 to the Mexican government, the massive statue traveled nearly 2,000 miles from Mexico City, only to be damaged in a fall when a cable hoisting it onto a truck snapped. President José López Portillo, his cabinet, military units, and an Arizona delegation had assembled in Mexico City to "escort" the statue to the border. Because the fall caused the figures of Villa and his horse to separate, the escort ceremony had to be rescheduled. News reports in Mexico compared this incident to the desecration of Villa's corpse.¹⁵ In 1926, three years after his death in Parral, Chihuahua, robbers broke into Villa's grave and removed his head, which has never been recovered and is rumored to be somewhere in the United States.¹⁶

When the emerging Chicano movement looked for heroes, they turned to Villa. In the mid-1960s, playwright Luis Valdez wrote the comedy *The Shrunken Head of Pancho Villa*, staged by many local community theater companies throughout the Southwest, including some in Tucson. The play used the decapitated head of Villa as a source that provided advice, inspiration, and a model for social resistance. It embodied the idea of surviving and speaking beyond death, showing that revolutionary ideals could persist and inspire action even when leadership or formal authority was gone. It also served as a tangible symbol of defiance against societal barriers and institutionalized oppression while functioning as a comic device that engaged audiences and commented on serious social and political challenges.¹⁷

The most significant mishap, though not the only challenge, resulted in a much-reduced ceremony to dispatch Villa's statue to the United States. Editorials and news coverage followed

¹² "Pancho Villa Finally Official Mexican Hero," *Citizen*, November 19, 1976, 15.

¹³ Luis Echeverría Álvarez, as quoted in Thomas Benjamin, *La Revolución: Mexico's Great Revolution as Memory, Myth, and History* (Austin: University of Texas Press, 2000), 135–136. Also see, "Pancho Villa Finally Officially Mexican Hero," *Citizen*, November 19, 1976, 15.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Matt Prichard, "Villa Statue on its Way Here Bringing Message of Peace," *Citizen*, May 7, 1981, 6C. John DeWitt, "Statue to be Erected in Tucson: Non-Violent Pancho Villa a Gift to Arizona," *Star*, March 21, 1981, B1, and Steve Meissner, "Villa Shot Out of Saddle: Statue Presentation Folds," *Star*, March 26, 1981, 1

¹⁶ Samuel Brunk, "Body Politics and the Figure of Pancho Villa: From the Mexican Revolution to the Present," *Foreign Affairs* 89, no. 3 (2010): 45–60.

¹⁷ Luis Valdez, *The Shrunken Head of Pancho Villa*, in *Necessary Theater: Six Plays about the Chicano Experience*, ed. Jorge A. Huerta (Houston: Arte Público Press, 1989), 142–207.

the statue's journey closely, and a few began to oppose Arizona's acceptance of the gift. Under the title "Pobre Pancho!" the *Star* ran a prominent editorial, which read: "A good many people are puzzled by the statue of Pancho Villa being presented to Arizona by the Mexican National Association of Newspapermen...But if it is a gag, it backfired when the bronze Pancho was knocked off his horse in an accident. When they got Pancho back in the saddle, he was too tall to get under a couple of highway overpasses on his journey northward. Newspaper people being who they are, don't be surprised if the American press comes up with a statue of Gen. John J. Pershing and presents it to Mexico. The gringos will be sure to check the height of the overpasses. It is something Old Black Jack would have done."¹⁸

Large crowds congregated to greet the statue "with enthusiasm" on its way to Tucson in Ciudad Juárez, Chihuahua, and El Paso, Texas, where it arrived in time to be part of the cities' Cinco de Mayo celebrations.¹⁹ When it crossed into the U.S., a representative of the Mexican National Press Association, which sponsored the trip, reiterated the intentions behind the gift: "Villa, who once brought violence to the United States, now in bronze brings a message of peace."²⁰ Despite Mexico's public sentiments emphasizing harmony, and Villa's popularity among Mexicans, the *Star* and *Citizen* often published detailed accounts of Villa's barbarous exploits and cruelty during the revolution. They made it clear that installing the statue in Tucson was intended to recast Villa's legacy, a project that some reporters refused to endorse. "From atop his horse," proclaimed the *Citizen*, "the fierce warrior could see the tall buildings of El Paso in the country to which he brought death and destruction 65 years ago."²¹

The Bronze Gift Reaches Tucson

A month before its arrival, the Tucson City Council finally decided to place the statue downtown. The official announcement declared that it would be placed in Eckbo Park, between Broadway and Congress, which confused many, including some city officials, who did not recognize a park by that name. San Francisco landscape architect Garrett Eckbo had designed the Tucson Community Center during urban renewal in the late 1960s.²² No one could explain how his name became linked with the park, but this confusion is indicative of the types of individuals city officials chose to celebrate and honor during that era.

The expressed hostility of some toward the statue prompted Governor Bruce Babbitt to defend his decision to accept it. He stated that, "I think history is always going to be quarreled over, written, and rewritten. When the people of Mexico offer us with enthusiasm a really magnificent statue of one of their genuine heroes, I think it would be fairly small of us to relive a lot of grievances."²³ His representative in Tucson, Augustine Garcia, echoed the governor's sentiments: "There is no question that it's a controversial issue, no question at all. But we've emphasized the fact that it's a gesture of friendship by the Mexican government."²⁴

A month and a half before the unveiling, the *Citizen* featured a long article titled, "Villa's Statue: Disgrace or Honor?" which provided those opposed to the statue an opportunity to voice their opinions. Focusing on two individuals who placed Villa beyond rehabilitation, the article began: "A statue of Pancho Villa, the famed Mexican revolutionary who was also a notorious

¹⁸ "Pobre Pancho!" (editorial), *Star*, March 30, 1981, A10.

¹⁹ Steve Meissner, "Viva Villa! He's Back in Bronze," *Star*; May 15, 1981, B1.

²⁰ Matt Prichard, "Pancho Villa has Message for Tucson," *Citizen*, May 6, 1981, C1.

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² Comment: "A Park for Pancho," *Star*; June 29, 1981, A10.

²³ Douglas Kreutz, "Villa's Statue: Disgrace or Honor?" *Citizen*, May 15, 1981, 1.

²⁴ *Ibid.*

bandit and ruthless killer will be a disgrace here, according to a noted University of Arizona historian and other Tucsonans.” It went on to highlight the sentiments of Bernard Fontana, a university ethnographer and historian, who said, “Villa did to some people in Sonora what Hitler did to people in some of those Polish towns. He massacred people. I think it’s a mistake to put up a statue in his honor... If you were to wander around the barrios, you would find that Villa is not popular with Sonorans and people who have roots in Sonora. It’s going to upset enough people that I wouldn’t be surprised if the statue would be in for a rough time.”²⁵ Despite not representing the lived experiences of those communities, Fontana assumed the authority to speak for Mexican and Sonoran people to the press. The article also included the perspective of Bernardo R. Acedo, an undergraduate at the University of Arizona, who opposed the statue based on what he had read about Villa’s actions, including the San Pedro de la Cueva Massacre, in which at least seventy-four people were killed in cold blood. Acedo stated, “I don’t think the statue should go up in Tucson. When a gift is offered by one country to another, it is difficult to say no. But a gift of a statue of a man who murdered and raped the people of an innocent village of Sonora? What is the meaning of such a gift?”²⁶

Although the *Citizen* provided far less coverage to supporters than it did to Fontana and Acedo, it included a few brief comments from a small number of individuals. Thomas O. Price, city operations director and of Mexican American descent, said, “I have no problem with it. Hundreds of people have seen it already, and many of those have been Mexican-Americans. I don’t think I have heard even one derogatory remark about it.” Ernesto Portillo, Sr., manager of bilingual radio station KXEW, was quoted as saying, “I think it is a positive step in reference to the improvement in international relations.”²⁷

Ethnographer Fontana had warned that a “rough time” awaited the statue, yet the opposition did not come from the barrios, Sonorans, or Mexican Americans as he predicted. Businessman Byron Ivancovich filed a complaint against the statue in the local court. He hired legal counsel, claiming misuse of taxpayer funds, and filed a lawsuit on June 2, 1981, to prevent the statue from being placed on city land at “city expense.” His lawyer justified his client’s actions as “based on Ivancovich’s feelings as a longtime Tucson resident with a knowledge of Southwestern history. He is quite versed in history, and he is unhappy with it from a historical viewpoint. He appreciates the fact that a lot of Mexican people look highly on Pancho Villa. But his historical viewpoint is different.” The lawsuit generated much publicity, prompting the governor’s aide Garcia to remind taxpayers that funds to install the statue came from “privately donated money in a special governor’s fund.”²⁸

Other municipalities saw Tucson’s controversy and Ivancovich’s lawsuit as an opportunity and contacted the governor and city officials to request that the gift be sent to their communities instead. In an article titled, “Move Unlikely: Others Willing to Put Pancho on a

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid. Acedo repeated information from Thomas H. Naylor’s article, published ten years earlier, “Massacre at San Pedro de la Cueva: The Significance of Pancho Villa’s Disastrous Sonora Campaign,” *Western Historical Quarterly*, 8.2 (April 1977): 125–150. This massacre is generally recognized as Villa’s bloodiest strike against civilians. In the midst of a civil war, the villagers of San Pedro de la Cueva mistook Villa’s soldiers for marauders and opened fired on them, killing several. Villa retaliated by ordering that all the adult males of the village be shot. Sixty-nine were killed. Villa then ordered the priest who begged for the life of the villagers to “never show his face again.” When he did, Villa shot the priest himself. See Katz, *Life of Villa*, 532–533. At various stages of the controversy, Naylor also came out publicly against the statue.

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Michael A. Chihak, “No Incidents Reported: Villa Statue Standing in Park,” *Citizen*, June 26, 1981, 14D.

Pedestal,” Garcia told the *Star* that “despite a less than hearty welcome from Tucson residents, Pancho Villa appears to be quite a popular fellow... We got all kinds of calls—from all over the place.” He singled out northern California and Texas and said, “El Paso was really adamant.” F. D. Fontes, the mayor of Nogales, Arizona, much closer to the border and able to gauge Sonoran sentiments toward Villa more fully, sent a letter to Tucson Mayor Lew Murphy that read, in part, “Since the city of Nogales has innumerable suitable locations, may I suggest that we come to your aid... with an offer to assume responsibility for this imposing creature.” This message was accompanied by a letter from the Nogales–Santa Cruz County Chamber of Commerce, which volunteered to pay the transportation costs for transporting the statue to its city. The chamber wrote, “We would welcome this gift from Mexico.” Garcia claimed that the lawsuit was no real index of the general sentiments toward the statue and stated that, “At this point, the opposition is fairly limited. There don’t appear to be a great number of people really opposed to it.”²⁹

While elected officials usually seize the chance to preside over major city ceremonies, Mayor Lew Murphy flatly refused to attend the Villa statue’s unveiling. He alerted the City Council, “I will be unavailable to attend the unveiling ceremony in any circumstances.” When asked if he would be out of town, Murphy advised, “No, I’ll just be unavailable. If you’re smart, you won’t attend.” Councilman Rudy Bejarano went on the record as saying he was proud to represent the city. At his urging, the council voted to take a three-hour recess so that they could attend the ceremony.³⁰

The statue was finally unveiled on June 30, 1981, before an international audience that included notables from both sides of the border. Twenty of Villa’s former comrades joined the crowd of over one thousand in the cry of “¡Viva Villa!” One of these was 86-year-old Adan Uro García, who insisted that “although he is aware of conflicting views about the revolutionary, in his mind Villa was and is a hero and great Mexican. The ideas Villa fought for were not just his own, but were the will of the Mexican people.” Mexican government representatives, along with two representatives of the Mexican Congress, were joined by one of Villa’s widows, two of Villa’s sons, and one daughter. General Raúl Madero, former Villa chief of staff and brother of former Mexican President Francisco Madero, also attended, as did the president of the Mexican Press Association. Arizona Governor Babbitt took the podium, and five members of the Tucson City Council attended. City Councilman Tom Volgy spoke on behalf of the City of Tucson. Some expressed their displeasure with Murphy’s boycott. A sign hanging from the footbridge that crosses over the park read, “¡Villa sí, Murphy no!”³¹ Local columnist Leyla Cattán, who emphasized the jubilant spirit that prevailed at the unveiling, correctly predicted that from that day forward, the small park would become known as “Pancho Villa Park.”³²

Those opposed to the statue still held out hope that Ivancovich's lawsuit would result in its removal. Ivancovich contended that “the statue caused him emotional distress” and that “it had caused downtown properties, in which he [had] a personal financial stake, to lose some of their value.” But that hope collapsed on April 6, 1983, nearly two years after the lawsuit was filed, when a Pima County Superior Court judge dismissed the case, ruling there was no basis for

²⁹ Cindy Hubert, “Move Unlikely: Others Willing to Put Pancho on a Pedestal,” *Star*, June 13, 1981, 1.

³⁰ Joe Burchell, “‘Mayor to be ‘Unavailable’ at Villa Statue Unveiling,” *Star*, June 26, 1981, 1.

³¹ Joe Burchell, “Villa Wins Another Campaign as Statue Gets Downtown Spot,” *Star*, July 1, 1981, A12. The *Star* reported that 650 people attended the unveiling; Chihak, “Villa in Place,” reported “more than 1,000.”

³² Leyla Cattán, “Estatuas de Pancho Villa piden en el suroeste de EU,” *Star*, July 26, 1981, E6.

claims that the city was “glorifying a murderer and rapist and thus corrupting public morals, driving consumers out of downtown Tucson and creating an eyesore.”³³

Community Defense and Symbolism

Many Mexican Americans continued to welcome the Villa statue, but Edward Tapia became its unofficial guardian. Tapia’s story appeared in the local papers and on local television news in 1983 when he personally responded to the statue’s defiling. Vandals had painted a yellow stripe down Villa’s back and the word “trash” on his horse. Passing the statue every morning on his way to work, Tapia made several calls to the Parks and Recreation Department requesting that it intervene and remove the paint. The director remembered that Tapia had called but explained that “because of the storm damage throughout the city, the statue cleanup was assigned and forgotten.” With no other recourse, Tapia took the matter into his own hands. On his day off work, he and his two young sons packed cleaning solvents and other equipment onto their truck and headed to the park.

They managed to scrub the paint off the horse and had just climbed their ladder to clean the yellow streak off Villa’s back when the police arrived. The officers immediately contacted the “right” people, and a work crew arrived later that afternoon. “I just got tired of seeing people laugh at the statue,” recalled an angry Tapia. “And I got tired of people passing the buck.” His momentary celebrity status brought him several anonymous and hostile phone calls. According to Tapia, they said “things like why don’t you get on the horse and ride off to Mexico?” Tapia said this was not the first time the statue had been vandalized and that he had seen remains of dried eggs and tomatoes on it. Raised in Tucson, Tapia explained what the statue meant to him and his family: “I’m sure [Villa] was not a saint. But, my father-in-law said he was a great general as far as military tactics were concerned. He fought for the campesinos [peasants], and anybody who fights for the poor is great. We don’t have many people like that anymore.”³⁴

Alongside Tapia, and shaped by generations of discrimination, Tucson writer Silviana Wood also embraced Villa as a hero. She based her fictional story *And Where Was Pancho Villa When You Really Needed Him?* on her experiences in a local public school. In Wood’s story, teachers unabashedly exchanged stories about their Mexican American students that highlighted “low expectations, low achievement, inflated grades, unrealistic goals.” After enduring discrimination and ridicule for being Mexican, the story’s protagonist seeks to escape from the hostile learning environment that envelops her. In the story, she recalls her teacher’s rationalization and absolution for violence and death when it served U.S. interests, including the dropping of the A-bomb that killed more than 100,000 Japanese. Her teacher’s words, “Sometimes you have to destroy in order to end the destruction,” stayed with her. With this rationalization for violence foremost in mind, and in the hopes of dismantling an actively racist system, the protagonist felt the need to call upon a daring hero. “So I waited for Pancho Villa to come charging into the room,” she recalls. The revolutionary responded to the summons, and the next day, students and school administrators returned to find her classroom in ruins.³⁵

³³ Shannon Travis, “Villa to Continue His Ride in City: Removal Denied,” *Citizen*, April 6, 1983, 1.

³⁴ Carmen Duarte, “When a Friend Gives You Something You Should Appreciate It’: Act of Respect for Pancho Villa: Statue Brings Out Mean Streak,” *Star*, August 19, 1983, B1.

³⁵ Silviana Wood, “And Where Was Pancho Villa When You Really Needed Him?” in *Puro Teatro: A Latina Anthology*, ed. Alberto Sandoval-Sánchez and Nancy Saporta Sternbach (Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2000), 191. Related to the sentiments express in Wood’s play, Southwest folklorist James Griffith’s research along the U.S.–Mexico border documents how Francisco Villa’s reputation shifted from historical actor to a moral figure invoked after death. Mexican people’s sentiments along both sides of the border, particularly those who have

Conclusion: Boundaries and Belonging

As immigration debates became more heated, those seeking to scapegoat Mexican immigrants in Arizona turned Villa into a symbol of the border crosser. In 1994, shortly after California voters passed Proposition 187, Tucsonan Don Barrington held a press conference in front of the Villa statue. He introduced a newly formed group, “Save Our State/Arizona,” and claimed that, “As in California, illegal immigrants in Arizona were draining the economy, crowding the state’s social services, and siphoning off its tax dollars. What is more, they were responsible for the state’s increase in rapes, murders, and drive-by shootings.” Pointing to the statue, Barrington cast Villa as an early example of a Mexican with no respect for international borders who nonetheless found a home in the United States.³⁶

To Barrington and others like him, who cast Villa as an archetypal border crosser, the statue operated as a “welcome mat” into the city, reinforcing their belief that Tucson allowed and even encouraged immigration. The Villa statue thus continues to prompt observers to confront and reconcile their own sentiments about boundaries and belonging. Historian John R. Gillis offers guidance that resonates with the statue and with southern Arizona as a corridor of entry for migrants: “We have no alternative but to construct new memories as well as new identities better suited to the complexities of the post-national era... In this era of plural identities, we need civil times and civil spaces more than ever, for those are essential to the democratic process by which individuals and groups come together to discuss, debate, and negotiate the past and, through this process, define the future.”³⁷ Although the Francisco “Pancho” Villa statue has often been a site of conflict rather than civility, it remains a rare example of public art that invites reflection on the realities and imaginaries of belonging in the U.S. and the possibility of multiple, overlapping national identities.

elevated Villa to sainthood, led Griffith to surmise that, “They ask Villa dead, to do what the living Villa legend was famous for—stand up for the underdog and confound his oppressor.” He makes this observation in *Folk Saints of the Borderlands: Victims, Bandits, and Healers* (Tucson: Rio Nuevo Publishers, 2003), 100.

³⁶ Tom Beal, “No Need for a Prop. 187 in Arizona,” *Star*, (editorial), November 17, 1994, A-19. Initiated by Protect Arizona Now, a more diluted version of legislation that Barrington proposed in 1994 was passed by Arizona voters in 2004. Proposition 200 sought to restrict access to public benefits by requiring state and local agencies to verify eligibility, a measure widely understood as targeting undocumented immigrants. It also imposed new voting requirements, including proof of citizenship to register and identification at the polls. The proposition was immediately challenged by civil rights groups, who argued that it created barriers for U.S. citizens and violated federal law.

³⁷ Gillis, *Commemoration*, 20.